

Two new combinations in Asian Ferns

Rajeev Kumar Singh and Vineet Kumar Rawat*

Botanical Survey of India, Arid Zone Regional Centre, AIIMS Road, Jodhpur, Rajasthan, India

*E-mail: rawat_vk2107@rediffmail.com; ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6828-5108>

Article Details: Received: 2025-08-30 | Accepted: 2025-11-24 | Available online: 2025-11-26

Licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License

Abstract: Two new combinations are proposed here in Asian ferns, one each in Marattiaceae and Ophioglossaceae. *Marattia paleolata* Alderw. from Sumatra is transferred to *Ptisana* Murdock and *Whittieria hengduanensis* Z.L.Liang & Li Bing Zhang from Sichuan is transferred to *Ophioglossum* L. These updates clarify the generic placement of both species.

Keywords: Endemic, *Marattia paleolata*, Marattiaceae, Ophioglossaceae, *Whittieria hengduanensis*

Introduction

The New World genus *Marattia* Sw. (Marattiaceae) consists of seven species, distributed in Brazil, Central America, Greater Antilles, Hawaiian Islands and Mexico (POWO, 2025). Species previously assigned to *Marattia* in the Old World are more appropriately placed in the Old-World genus *Ptisana* Murdock. Accordingly, *Marattia paleolata* Alderw., described from Sumatra, Indonesia, is here formally transferred to *Ptisana*.

The cosmopolitan genus *Ophioglossum* L. comprises about 64 species (POWO, 2025). Recently, Zhang & Zhang (2022) erected three segregate genera, *Goswamia*, *Haukia* and *Whittieria*, within *Ophioglossum*. However, these taxa cannot be clearly distinguished from the morphologically cohesive and monophyletic *Ophioglossum*. Therefore, *Whittieria hengduanensis* Z.L.Liang & Li Bing Zhang, described from Sichuan, China, is here transferred to *Ophioglossum*.

New combinations

Marattiaceae

Ptisana paleolata (Alderw.) R.Kr.Singh & V.K.Rawat, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Marattia paleolata* Alderw., Bull. Jard. Bot. Buitenzorg Sér. 2, 23: 16. 1916.

Holotype: Indonesia, Sumatra, Mount Singgalang, C.G. *Matthew* 662 (BO).

Distribution: Endemic to Sumatra, Indonesia.

Ophioglossaceae

Ophioglossum hengduanensis (Z.L.Liang & Li Bing Zhang) R.Kr.Singh & V.K.Rawat, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Whittieria hengduanensis* Z.L.Liang & Li Bing Zhang, *PhytoKeys* 249: 31. 2024.

Holotype: China, Sichuan, Yajiang County, Jiaonibao Village, 2750 m, 30°6'10.93"N, 101°1'49.79"E, 15 July 2021, Z.-L. Liang, L.-S. Jiang & Q. Yu LZL1959 (CDBI).

Distribution: Endemic to Sichuan, China.

Acknowledgements

The authors are thankful to the Director, Botanical Survey of India, Kolkata and Head of Office, Botanical Survey of India, Arid Zone Regional Centre, Jodhpur for facilities.

References

- POWO. (2025). Plants of the World Online. Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew. Available from: <http://www.plantsoftheworldonline.org/> (accessed 24 August 2025).
- Zhang L. and Zhang L.B. (2022). Phylogeny, character evolution, and systematics of the fern family Ophioglossaceae based on Sanger sequence data, plastomes, and morphology. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution* 173: 107512. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ympev.2022.107512>